

Comparing Learning Objects from one “worldwide” and two African Open Educational Resource repositories using the Learning Object Review Instrument (LORI) v. 1.5

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Abstract. In light of increasing emphasis on both localization and globalization of information technology and equal access to educational opportunities for all people, online Open Educational Resources (OER) are considered to be a promising approach for promoting free and adaptable education access to instructors and learners around the world. Wide variation in the quality and content of repository websites available in different communities indicates a need to investigate the similarities and differences between the Learning Objects (LOs) offered. A systematic comparison of three websites with contributors and end-users in Africa and around the world provides a clearer picture of how a community’s needs and resources inform OER availability and offerings. This project reviews OERAfrica.org, TESSAfrica.net (Teacher Education in sub-Saharan Africa), and OERcommons.org, using the categories of design, intended audience, and rank of five LOs per site using the Learning Object Review Instrument (LORI Version 1.5).

Resumo. À luz da crescente ênfase na localização e globalização do tecnologia da informação e no acesso mais igualitário de recursos educacionais para todas as pessoas, os Recursos Educacionais Abertos (REA) disponíveis online são cada vez mais considerados uma abordagem promissora para a promoção de um acesso a conteúdos educacionais livres e adaptáveis às necessidades de professores e estudantes de todo o mundo. Uma grande variação na qualidade e no conteúdo dos repositórios web disponíveis em diferentes comunidades e grupos indicam uma necessidade de se investigar as semelhanças e diferenças entre os Objetos de Aprendizagem(OA) oferecidos nesses repositórios. Uma istemática de três websites com colaboradores e usuário-final localizados na África e ao redor do mundo irá proporcionar uma imagem mais clara de como as necessidades e recursos de uma comunidade informam a disponibilidade e as ofertas de Recursos Educacionais Abertos. Esse projeto analisa os sites OERAfrica.org, TESSAfrica.net (Ensino de Professores na África Sub-Sahariana; *Teacher Education in sub-Saharan Africa*) e OERcommons.org, usando as

categorias de design, público-alvo e categoria de cinco Objetos de Aprendizagem por site usando o Instrumento de Análise de Objetos de Aprendizagem (LORI, Versão 1.5).

Introduction

Education is an internationally accepted human right (United Nations Children’s Fund, 2007) and leaders in countries around the world strive to provide education and training opportunities, often trying to draw from few available resources. Many developing countries with numerous demands on limited technology and other resources are becoming increasingly flexible in methods used to provide educational opportunities for learners and teachers. Learning Objects (LO), a type of digital educational resource (Friesen, 2004), potentially provide a way to offer educational materials free or at low cost to learners especially when offered as an open, or shareable, commodity (Kelty, 2008). As Friesen (2009) discusses, although LO and Open Educational Resources (OER) are generally considered separate in theory, these labels are often used interchangeably in practice. In countries without a history of debating the LO versus the OER movement, the practicality of the commodity might trump the specific label. For this paper, the term OER will be used primarily although the instrument for comparing material from OER repository websites is called the Learning Object Review Instrument (LORI v. 1.5; Nesbit, Belfer, & Leacock, 2003). This paper will refer to the instrument as LORI, a shortened name for LORI v. 1.5.

In many countries struggling uphold their Education for All (EFA) commitment to offer quality education to all children (United Nations News Centre, 2007) OER may be one of few efficient options for quickly disseminating information to a great number of aspiring teachers and learners. However, due to the wide range of choices for OER from around the world, additional training in how to locate and use OER materials has become a priority for many communities. An increasing number of communities offer or attend specialized

workshops on international OER and “e-learning tools” use and acquisition (Alikhan, 2011). Once a trusted OER source is found it can be challenging to provide locally relevant education that also takes advantage of the increasingly available international education resources. Internationalization makes it imperative that OER and other educational materials be *high-quality, accessible, and malleable* enough to be useful in a wide range of cultures.

The purpose and organization of online OER repositories varies greatly according to the vision and mission of the site and interest of the contributors and users. Whereas the free-form structure of many repositories invites a variety of formats for posted material, it must be considered that lack of website organization and OER criteria can limit the usefulness of the repository by decreasing the chances of finding relevant OER for search terms. The LORI provides a framework to conduct reviews and systematic comparisons. For this exploratory study this instrument was used to investigate website-repositories hosted by three organizations: OER Africa (OERA), OER Commons (OERC), and Teacher Education in Sub-Saharan Africa OER (TESSA). Comparing the material on these OER repository websites illustrates the multiple contexts that must come together to provide useful educational materials to learners across cultures. These contexts include, but are not limited to, funding sources, trainers and teachers, creators of software/hardware/internet technology, end-users, and designers.

Due to cost and time limitations, most designers of cross-culturally directed OERs cannot personally travel to all sites where the material will be used. In fact, many sites with cross-cultural audiences offer materials from countries far from the end-users. A look to the evolution of the OER movement indicates potential areas of growth and research for offering increasingly accessible materials for all users regardless of where the OER originated.

A Brief History of the OER Movement

The term “Open Educational Resource” originated in 2002 during a United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) forum sponsored by William and Flora Hewlett Foundation (WFHF) (Wiley, 2007). In the same year, Creative Commons (CC) was launched, helping to pave the way for increased creation and dissemination of low-cost and free digital OERs (Kelty, 2008). The CC licensing approach provided a user-friendly mechanism of shifting content licensing toward collaborations between creators who could share responsibility and benefit of their work without the restrictions and costs of traditional licensing (Kelty, 2008). Funding provided by the WFHF for nearly a decade has propelled the creation of numerous OER repository websites beginning in the mid-to-late 2000’s. These sites include OERA, OERC, and TESSA albeit indirectly through a comprehensive OER research and development project by the UK Open University (Wolfenden, Buckler, & Keraro, 2008).

A December 2005 UNESCO Forum on Educational Planning, also funded by WFHF, included 480 participants from 90 countries who, for over six weeks and 700 posts, addressed the need for improved support for OER use amongst teachers in developing countries compared with those in industrialized countries with high levels of technology (Stacey, 2007). Specific suggestions from participants in developing countries included:

- assurance of a high level of commitment to ensure quality across languages,
- easier navigation to locate appropriate LOs,
- supported research process for individuals without much formal schooling,
- improved support for teachers to use OER efficiently, and
- whether to invest in managing a lack of a pedagogical base.

Each of these suggestions speaks to the hope for the equalizing potential of OER and to the concerns about how developing countries can minimize possible barriers with the support of the western countries that are generally the source for these repositories. These concerns raised in 2005 are just now beginning to be addressed as they have persisted for over six years. This exploratory study aims to gather information that may further illuminate issues pertaining to access to OER for all people.

In 2010, CC officially embraced the OER movement by linking the two previously separate organizations to improve funding options and awareness of OER (Linksvayer, 2010). Clearly stated licensing expectations and support for international digital information dissemination are expected to improve opportunities for more individuals, schools, and other organizations to access the benefits of sharing and co-creating OER to be used by other learners and teachers around the world (Park, 2010).

Why Africa?

Currently, multiple Africa-focused OER repository websites provide free materials to anyone with access to technology. However, as discussed during the 2005 UNESCO OER forum, Africa, and more specifically, Sub-Saharan Africa, is a region consistently mentioned as an area of need. This was due to great numbers of people living in high levels of poverty with few life-sustaining resources (Stacey, 2007). The UN efforts to ensure education for all people have motivated many governments to change expectations for children who will need education in order to access more career options in adulthood (Republic of Rwanda, 2000).

With radical lifestyle shifts associated with mass movement from agrarian toward industrial society (Cardoso, 2009), children are often caught in the middle of radical lifestyle shifts associated with mass movement from agrarian

toward industrial society. These youngest members of society may be expected to fulfill the expectations of both family dependence on their labor and increasing social responsibilities to attend school, often an additional expense for families.

For children who are able to attend, the schools themselves may offer students and teachers limited physical and technological infrastructure (Weber, 2009). Additionally, the AIDS epidemic has impacted teachers particularly heavily, creating a situation where many trained teachers are becoming too sick to work even as more children are expected to attend school (Wolfenden et al., 2008).

Globalization, Localization, and Glocalization

Worldwide, access to income is increasingly dependent on one's ability to operate sophisticated technology and communicate knowledgeably. Increased education and communication opportunities have dual roles of building and restructuring the areas within which people live their lives, at times blending local practices with global expectations. Individuals and communities are increasingly mobile, convergent, and interactive (Jansson, 2007). As work and leisure activities shift toward immediacy and product personalization, classic radio and television broadcast formats give way to "narrowcasts," choice-driven technological interaction using mobile phones and/or the internet.

Communication using personal technology is at an all-time high, with 1/3 of the people in developing countries owning cellular phones (UN, 2010). Without leaving their local communities, a growing number of individuals have ready access to and can exchange ideas with people far removed from their immediate environment.

Digital information and communications technology (ITC) practices facilitate a merge of previously separate concepts, for example, public-private, send-receive, and global-local (Jansson, 2007). Glocalization, a mix of *global* frameworks and *local* practices, greatly increases the potential for independent learning by merging worldwide and local knowledge (Weber, 2009). A particularly poignant case of the adjustment demanded by glocalization is when

Disney opened in Paris, expecting identical employee behavior as their other internationally known locations. The Parisian employees and patrons similarly rejected the global way until the Disney leaders agreed to change some expectations to respect local Parisian culture (Matusitz, 2010). In order to succeed in attracting employees and customers in Paris EuroDisney needed to glocalize, to find a way to meet their global company's branding needs while respecting the local culture. Although it can be argued this scenario was extreme, it clearly shows the negotiation that can follow potential emotional impacts of introducing new social expectations into a country.

Individuals make meaning of their experiences and the introduction of new technology can challenge or confuse previously held personal and cultural beliefs. At first it might seem that more knowledge and technological access would automatically lead to improved lives for more people. However, there are concerns about the effects of experiences such as glocalization on individuals and communities who may be at greater risk of experiencing feelings of anomie. Anomie is a Durkheimian concept describing the individual and communal sense of disorientation caused by system-level exposure to too many new, foreign ideas in too short a time (Atteslander, 2007). Some individuals and families, when the thrill of learning the new information fades, may be left with an uncomfortable sense that the new information does not integrate with their traditional ways but that they are powerless to return to traditional ways. Without a recognizable connection to previously held relationships and identities, individuals may lose their cultural compass and their ability to enjoy the "progress" (Atteslander, 2007). There is also some concern that providing access to previously unattainable foreign-source education will negatively alter the existing routines and power structures in traditional societies (Nsamenang, 2005). For instance, choosing to delay childbearing for educational attainment can improve income prospects for individuals while also changing fertility patterns in some previously agriculture-centric countries such as Kenya (Schreffler & Doodoo, 2009). With planning, these worries may be minimized or even alleviated by innovators such

as OER designers who can make it a priority to take a respectful approach to each culture and include traditional elements and examples when possible (Nsamenang, 2005).

Open Educational Resources and OER Repository Websites

In communities with few education resources, a dependable supply of quality OER materials can efficiently support well-rounded learning if there is access for growing numbers of people (Wiley & Gurrell, 2009). The information contained within the OER may be useful but without a basic learning process or guided welcome to OER, end-users may have trouble applying the material to their lessons, or their lives, in a cohesive manner (Welsh & Sapire, 2008). Three websites described below each abide by their own operational standards, offer varying degrees of navigational planning within their repositories, and provide access to different numbers and types of OER.

OER Commons, started in 2007, promotes the use of OER to disseminate education throughout the world in an equitably accessible manner. Intending to be a single source of readily available resources to teachers and learners across the learning spectrum, the website has grown to include easily searchable terms, links to other OER sites, and a relatively clear system of reviewing and editing digital content housed on the site. Due to the high number of items within widely divergent learning categories, someone hoping for a quick search may benefit from taking time to become familiar with the site and stay focused to locate tools that meet predetermined goals.

OER Africa, started in April, 2010, is a service funded by the Hewlett Foundation in conjunction with the South African Institute for Distance Education (SAIDE). Intended for "African Academics" across the continent, the overarching goal of this website repository is to build and develop African societies and economies by facilitating collaboration networks around OER. Guided by the expectation that educational resources are infinite and generative

rather than finite and diminishing, it is expected that short-term investment in OER can remove barriers to education over time. An embedded webpage about finding OER offers a search resource which can make it easier to link to content on and outside of the website.

TESSA, Teacher Education in Sub-Saharan Africa (TESSA), with its first published newsletter in April, 2007, is a sponsored research and development project intended to create and disseminate materials to guide teachers and teacher educators in that region. This multilingual website offers numerous free Creative Commons licensed materials that are readily adaptable between countries in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). Designed in collaboration with Open University, UK, this is a pre-planned site with templates and other materials to facilitate standardized formatting of print, audio, and visual resources (Wolfenden et al., 2010). Unlike the other two OER repositories mentioned above, the original materials for TESSA were constructed in a coordinated process involving teachers and teacher educators across SSA. The learning materials were subsequently traded for peer review amongst the teachers and teacher educators who could provide feedback and add country-specific examples to ensure a good fit with local populations. Guided by the research nature of the project, the practices come about through explicit planning of templates, requesting original documents be written by African educators who represent multiple countries, and allowing a guided series of changes while retaining the original purpose of each OER. These are intended for on-the-ground teacher educators and teachers themselves. Each module offers options for all individuals regardless of a greater or lesser access to computing technology.

This exploratory study uses materials from the above-mentioned three OER repository websites to compare electronic learning materials intended for users locally and globally, in Africa and worldwide. Although the sites use the CC licensing scheme, each offers a unique web design and OER options which greatly influence the user experience.

Learning Object Review Instrument (LORI)

LORI is the second incarnation of a measure created by Canadian researchers to determine and influence the quality and utility of LOs by rating components of learning and accessibility at a metadata level (Nesbit, Belfer, & Leacock, 2003). LORI contains nine dimensions rated on a 1-5 Likert scale. The points from each section are added for a sum total. The total score allows for comparison of OER materials on an over-all usability level. For this section describing the LORI domains, the OER materials sampled will be called LO. According to Nesbit et al. (2003), “learning objects are information resources or interactive software used in online learning. A single image, page of text, an interactive simulation, or an entire course could all be examples” (p. 2). This description allowed for nearly any resource found on the three repositories to be included in the review.

The domains and ratings (5 highest; 1 lowest) offered by LORI:

1. *Content Quality* (is provided information free of errors and bias?)

- 5: No errors; presented without bias or omissions; logical argument for each claim; sensitive to cultural differences
- 3: Mostly correct but lack of clarity that can mislead users
- 1: Material is incorrect and/or misleading, has informational or cultural bias, lacks appropriate detail; lack of emphasis on critical information

2. *Learning Goal Alignment* (degree to which each component of the LO supports a stated learning goal)

- 5: A learning goal is clearly present and learner is supported by LO
- 3: Lack of appropriate information to answer questions, meet learning goal
- 1: Lack of learning goal, or inappropriate for intended learners

3. *Feedback and Adaptation* (degree of response to user input)

- 5: Takes individual user into account by providing responses matched to the learner's needs for answer correction
- 3: Correct answers are provided with an indication about which questions the user answered incorrectly
- 1: Does not take the learner into account for either answer correction or teaching alternatives

4. *Motivation* (is this LO interesting and engaging to users?)

- 5: Interesting to intended learners; offers choice, humor, life-like activities with relevant feedback and natural consequences
- 3: Lack of interesting narration; lack challenging learning opportunities and opportunities to control outcomes
- 1: irrelevant content; inappropriate challenge level; interference from the LO features; lack of choice

5. *Presentation Design* (visual and audio information designed to improve learning)

- 5: Production quality enhances learning; easily readable text; learning goals supported by audio and visual components; accurate
- 3: Lack of clear connection between text and visuals
- 1: Production quality interferes with learning; headings confusing or meaningless to learners

6. *Interaction Usability* (is the layout easy to navigate and predictable?)

- 5: User interface intuitive and explicit; logical; consistent; minimal lag
- 3: User interface works but does not enhance learning; inconsistent labeling

- 1: Many parts not working or lag significantly; lacks instructions

7. *Accessibility* (is the resource easy to use for persons with disabilities as well as those without)

- 5: Significant levels of support for learners with disabilities; accessible using assistive means; IMS guidelines for Accessible Learning at AAA level
- 3: HTML page with animation embedded and captions when appropriate; does not define acronyms; W3C level A
- 1: Lack of visual support for audio or audio support for video; color differentiation necessary to read chart

8. *Reusability* (is the resource easily transferred a variety of contexts and adaptable for users with diverse backgrounds?)

- 5: Useful with or without additional materials; transferable to multiple courses without alteration; included glossaries & prerequisite content statements make it applicable to a range of learners
- 3: Specific to users and contexts due to limited vocabulary and examples
- 1: Refers to originating organization limiting its generalizability; requires other resources to be useful; demands high level of prior knowledge

9. *Standards Compliance* (abides by international standards for LOs)

- 5: Meets all international standards for metadata and technical requirements (IMS, IEE, SCORM, and W3C); metadata included within LO and separate page
- 3: Meets some international standards for metadata tests but not compliance

1: Misses all relevant international standards

Eight of the nine LORI domains listed above were relevant for this project comparing five LO samples from each of three OER repositories. The *Standards Compliance* domain is not included due to lack of training and access to standards support. This is not expected to interfere with the findings since each site was sampled and scored without that domain. Additionally, the domains allowing for a non-digital application of a resource were most applicable for this project even if a high score was not possible in all domains. For example, the *Feedback & Adaptability* domain, when a LO includes feedback individualized to the learner it will receive a high rating (5). A LO with an answer key for quiz, problem set, activity, or other way to test learning, the LO will be acknowledged for that by earning a middle rating (3). Without an answer key for a quiz, problem set, activity, or other way to test learning, the LO would earn a low rating (1).

Method: Comparing LOs from three repositories

The manual separates the rating sections from the description sections so the first step was to use the LORI domains and items described above to create a table on a spreadsheet where the rating descriptions were visible at the same time as the recording section with the Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5. After studying the manual to become familiar with the item scoring process it was time to move to the next step.

To locate five LOs for each of three websites there was a systematic search and collect process intended to retrieve qualifying resources in a random manner. The primary selection process was that the first five sampled were considered representative of their originating repository website as long as each LO met specific criteria: English language (Anglophone) and educational (they could not be advertisements for other school programs, for instance). After first

opening one computer browser window for each website this author spent 45 minutes navigating through the pages to locate, download, and save copies of the English language LOs as they appeared.

The use of a limited number of specific search procedures allowed for obtaining representative LOs with education-related topics for comparison. Due to the difference of layout for each repository, additional criteria were added that was unique for each. For OERC the search criteria were the words “Africa” and “education” not including LO directly from OER Africa or TESSA links. For OERA, the search methods included using headings related to educational material (to exclude health LO housed on the same website repository). The TESSA repository is specifically targeted toward educational materials with clear directions for accessing the LOs, or “modules”, such that no special search criteria were needed.

The 15 sample LOs represent multiple teaching approaches for a range of content. Examples include: an academic conference poster about growing grains in state in the United States by three authors that was uploaded onto the site with no accompanying material; a hundred-page manual to train teachers how to teach math to students from a range of ages; and a three-page tutorial on teaching literacy to young children complete with case studies and additional resources.

After downloading and saving the five samples collected from each site it was time to review each LO with the Review Instrument. For each repository, the group of five from each site was reviewed sequentially in the order they were downloaded. Only then it was time to progress to the next LO sample. This allowed for assurance that if the preliminary screening during the selection process missed a disqualifying criterion, it would be simple to track which site needed a replacement LO. No LO replacement was needed as each LO from the original sample proved to have met all criteria.

Each LO was reviewed with the same process, rated with each domain of the LORI before moving on to the next, starting with Content Quality and

ending with Reusability. The domain scores for each LO were tallied to provide an overall score. This allowed for comparison between LOs as well as items. Each had a unique combination of LORI - rated strengths and weaknesses that provided insight into how the LO might be lacking or complete depending on the needs of the end-user(s).

Using LORI provided a cohesive method of comparing material from three OER repositories, OER Africa, OER Commons, and TESSA OER. Scores showed that of the three repository websites studied, TESSA site's requirements for formatting, such as templates with minimum quantities of specific criteria, seemed to be the source of the most consistent and self-contained units for education. When constructing and posting material, OER designers who keep their potential end-user in mind will better ensure their material is useful to others who may not be able to access the information in other ways.

Results

A look at the patterns show that TESSA scored highest in each domain. OER Commons scored next highest with a two low performing LOs bringing down the overall rating. OER Africa scored the lowest of the three sites due to numerous low (1) scores throughout. Consistent low scores in domains of learning goals, learner feedback, access, and reusability differentiated this LO sample from the other two. Looking to Figure 1 for ratings of each LO shows ratings for each item and the sum total for each LO sample. The bottom right corner provides a total score for each repository website, obtained by adding together the domain totals from each LO. Possible points for the total site are as follows: OER Africa scored 105/200; OER Commons scored 121/200; TESSA scored 140/200.

	Content	LG Align	Feedback	Motivate	Design	Usability	Access	Reusable	Total/40
OERA 1	1	1	1	1	3	5	1	1	14
OERA 2	1	1	1	1	3	5	1	3	16
OERA 3	5	5	3	5	5	5	1	5	34
OERA 4	4	1	1	4	2	3	1	1	17
OERA 5	5	5	3	3	5	1	1	1	24
									105/200
OERC 1	5	5	4	5	5	5	1	5	35
OERC 2	5	1	1	4	3	5	4	3	26
OERC 3	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	10
OERC 4	5	3	3	4	1	4	4	5	29
OERC 5	5	5	2	3	3	1	1	1	21
									121/200
TESSA 1	5	5	3	3	5	5	1	5	32
TESSA 2	5	5	3	4	5	3	4	4	33
TESSA 3	3	3	3	3	3	5	1	4	25
TESSA 4	5	3	1	3	3	3	1	4	23
TESSA 5	5	3	3	3	3	4	1	5	27
									140/200

Figure 1. LORI Scores for OERC, OERA, and TESSA

Discussion

This exploratory study found consistent differences in the quality, usability, and accessibility of LOs offered on the three OER repository websites as assessed with LORI's items of Content Quality, Learning Goal Alignment, Feedback & Adaptation, Motivation, Presentation Design, Interaction Usability, Accessibility, and Reusability. The higher ratings for the TESSA LOs may indicate the benefit of planning and providing templates when it comes to creating and offering LOs to enhance learning. Despite the guidance provided by TESSA the ratings were not perfect and might indicate some measure of flexibility for contributing authors. Overall, for the five TESSA LOs rated, the weakest area was Accessibility, the strongest was Reusability. These two ratings likely share a single factor: the emphasis on non-technical methods of acquisition and dissemination are a mismatch with the LORI which focuses on sharing LOs. The high Reusability factor was likely due to TESSA's mandatory simple templates and use of Microsoft Office Word, both to allow for easy printing and dissemination.

The slightly lower overall LORI ratings for OER Commons may have been caused by a single sample LO that scored very low in all but one item. The highest score was in the Content Quality, the lowest was a tie for Feedback and Accessibility. OER Commons is a well-established repository with monitored submissions, rating systems, and clear guidelines for what is acceptable. Its efforts to become the worldwide OER repository have increased the number of LOs into the thousands by offering its own LO as well as connections that directly link to other sites such as TESSA and OER Africa.

OER Africa scored the lowest overall, due to a few low performing LOs. Compared to the resources on the other two repositories, OERA seemed to have the most varied content with a higher percentage of the sampled LO not meeting the education criteria during the sampling process. This is where a few advertisements for other schools were found posted as OER during the sample selection process. One example of a resource that met the education criteria but

that some might not consider a self-contained LO is a stand-alone re-appropriated conference poster discussing farming in a Midwestern US state. This might have been useful to some teachers but did not provide a complete learning experience as rated by the LORI. Interaction Usability rated highest while the domains of Feedback & Adaptability, Accessibility, and Reusability rated lowest. The resources were useful for their intended use but may not provide a cohesive learning experience for the end user without instructor guidance.

In this review process, much was learned about using the LORI and about the three repositories included in the sampling process. Limitations of this study include using an instrument that is not well known, comparing websites across cultures, and having only one reviewer. Future iterations of this study should rate a larger sample of LO from each included repository and account for inter-rater reliability by including two or more raters who have come to agreement with the LORI ratings. Additionally, for cross-cultural comparisons of LOs, having a native speaker translate the LOs from their original language into English or translate the LORI into another language. Either of these comparisons will likely provide a more accurate representation of the LOs as they are used in the country or region of study. It may be important to have a cultural liaison to ensure appropriate and accurate translation that accounts for local nuances

The LORI offers a set of useful items to compare LO. With the increasing use of digital OER as educational materials on local and global levels within small and large organizations (UN, 2011) it would be useful to have a widely-used rating system with which to compare OER from different authors that are located on different repository sites. Even if developing countries do not have ready access to the technology for more advanced use of digital LO, including a rating system early in the promotion process will likely support higher quality services over time. That said, maintaining cultural respect is crucial when trying to balance global, local, and glocal elements of learning.

It is important to question whether automated translations are sufficient to

provide a representative picture of how the original would score on a standardized measure in another language. The LORI team endeavored to use this instrument across cultures (Li, Nesbit, & Richards, 2006) and their approach emphasized efficiency rather than quality of translating a LO from one language to another. Using a computer program called *Zope Localizer* (Richter, 2005) to translate the LORI into different languages allowed the authors to test their efforts to promote cross-cultural communities for sharing metadata and ratings about LO. The authors chose to use Chinese [sic] and French versions of the LORI providing the explanation that these languages are widely represented by individual websites. The authors are aware that despite their intentions efforts to provide a structure for cross-cultural engagement did not fully meet their expectations. Using LORI did meet their goal of supporting collaborative rating and sharing of metadata about individual LOs within separate repositories. However, the content of ratings and the decision to merge communities of practice (teacher groups or administrators, for instance) with ethnically and geographically diverse communities seemed to decrease the depth of understanding between the groups being studied. The authors suggested that future approaches might benefit from shifting focus toward local rather than universal translation practices.

Too few research projects focusing solely on local practices show that being too self-contained can also limit understanding. Although there have been reports from projects comparing LOs and other OERs between countries in Africa (Wolfenden et al., 2010; McKenney & van den Akker, 2005) these reports rarely compare their materials with that of other research teams. Additionally, the research and reports are generally conducted by organizations based outside of Africa, even if Africans are directly included in the data collection, analysis, and publishing processes. Ideally the successful dissemination of these reports will attract more research funding for African organizations to conduct their own research to officially disseminate locally and abroad beyond the traditional university location that is often limited to a university audience (Maclure, 2006).

On the other hand, with the increasingly international cries for African success it is important to respect African ways of life that may not directly integrate with increasing standards of evidence-based practice and more Western ways of categorizing the world (Nsamenang, 2005).

Conclusion

Despite obvious cultural limitations that English is not likely the first language for many OER users intended for audiences in non-English dominant cultures, using an English-only approach garnered valuable information about the structure of the OER repositories. The findings also provided insight into possible avenues for investigating and supporting these repositories in the future. The only repository website reviewed in this study that consistently used materials from African authors was TESSA. In order to submit materials it is necessary to have signed up as a member of TESSA and to follow their stringent requirements for what can be included and how it must be constructed. Some might argue that this site is not actually “open” due to the constraints on content and formatting. Despite the lack of variety in content and form, this meets the goals of the site, teaching educators in Sub-Saharan Africa. Wiley (2000) discusses the importance of using LO for learning within a coordinated educational plan, not just to provide a unique interest-grabbing component. TESSA OER is a prime example of a coordinated educational plan that focuses on functionality to the end-user.

Nearly 10 years after the OER movement began digital media and LOs are widely expected to help developing countries reach international education goals and standards that will promote successful entry into the global knowledge economy. With appropriate aid and planning, Sub-Saharan Africa will likely benefit from online repository websites that can provide digital OERs at low cost.

Additionally, a standardized measuring system that provides a culturally

sensitive summary of OER strengths and weaknesses can support improved judgment of which materials are high quality and useful to the population. Although not ready in its present generic form, with some updates and local cultural input the LORI may be a worthy candidate for tracking progress of LO development and dissemination.

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